

Master's Thesis On

**“CROWDFUNDING OF EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGY STARTUPS IN
INDIA”**

***FOR THE PARTIAL FULFILLMENT OF THE REQUIREMENT
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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that the Master’s Thesis “Crowdfunding of education technology startups in India” has been prepared by Mr. Abhishek Anand under my supervision and guidance. The project report is submitted towards the partial fulfilment of 2 years, Full-time Master of Business Administration.

Name & Signature of Faculty

Date

DECLARATION

I, ABHISHEK ANAND, Roll No.20GSOB2010161, student of School of Business, Galgotias University, Greater Noida, hereby declares that the Master’s Thesis on “Crowdfunding of education technology startups in India” is an original and authenticated work done by me.

I further declare that it has not been submitted elsewhere by any other person in any of the institutes for the award of any degree or diploma.

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ABSTRACT

Over the past decades, technology has made a significant contribution to the development of education and has had a profound effect on school education in India. The Government of India has placed appropriate emphasis on Education (ET) technology in successive national education policies. Until 2019, Edtech did not attract enough funding, but the Covid-19 epidemic accelerated online learning and gave birth to a few EdTech start-ups in India and around the world. These Edtech companies have been around for almost two decades and promised a bright future in education. It is believed that education is one of the main sources of prosperity for millions of people living in Asian countries.

However, the main method of delivery did not change fundamentally in the long run. Although some institutions have begun to use digital technology, the education sector is slow to embrace and implement the new age technology in its system. The same was true on the basis that the digital education system could eliminate the jobs of a few teachers, at least in school education. This current study aims to map out the current state of EdTech in India and their prospects. The current study also examines the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and challenges (SWOC) linked to Edtech companies after covid-19.

INTRODUCTION

The Covid-19 epidemic, in some ways, forced the world to replace traditional face-to-face reading with online or visual learning. It was a time of change and gave a chance for a few Edtech companies to thrive, taking over the epidemic. “Many of the words (online reading, open reading, web-based reading, e-learning, mixed reading, m-reading, for example.) Are like the ability to use a computer connected to a network, providing the ability to read anywhere, anytime, at any time. rhythm, by any means”. The flexibility and simplicity that comes with remote learning mode will probably arouse interest and anticipation of online learning with a mixed model soon. However, the line between classroom-based reading and visual reading will undoubtedly narrow or at least darken. If the gap between traditional and online education is closed, it will bring immediate results to GER and the changing changes in higher education. Higher education, with its emphasis on academic study, can be a powerful force for good background.

Although high school students were accustomed to reading visually, traditional institutions were not yet ready to face the digital challenge. The purpose of distance education prior to the epidemic was to provide access to students who had been deprived of traditional education in schools, colleges or universities. The purpose of elementary education was to bring about equality in society. Online learning aims to make the learning-teaching process more focused on students and create a flexible environment using digital tools and modern communication networks. Online learning allows students to access learning without being in one place, campus, or local region.

CROWDFUNDING OF EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGY STARTUPS IN INDIA

Edtech companies that accumulate sponsorship on social media are ten pennies right now. We wanted to be able to dig a little deeper and understand how investor react to edtech programs on these sites.

Crowdfunding is a fundraiser where creators of an idea or business or community project ask for financial support from strangers who want to participate by developing small amounts of money to get the latest prize. Remember that crowdfunding only helps sponsorships, but not the process of creating or distributing sponsored product or services.

While crowdfunding brings as the new thing the fact that it is done online, it is not a new approach. It already existed before the advent of the internet and came from sponsoring and promoting projects by the community. Undoubtedly it was crowdfunding "offline". It was a gift from the French people to the American people and represented freedom.

Crowdfunding also stands for that freedom, in the sense that it allows for retirement to depend on the many institutions that have so far hindered the efficiency of entrepreneurs when presenting their own projects. It is part of a business-based practice among people, from which consultants are removed.

In December 2006, there were no business angels investing in startups in Spain. Government institutions did not support new projects in new technologies or the Internet, as ENISA, CDTI, and others now do; and there were no special investment funds at first, although there were technology entrepreneurship projects.

From the Internet bubble: From 2000 to 2005 almost no one dared to invest in the network. However, in 2005 there was a resurgence powered by new trends from Silicon Valley and the beginning of social media and e-commerce. At that time there were entrepreneurs who wanted to do things, but there were no investors or banks or institutions to support them. Entrepreneurs therefore consider investing in "2.0 web companies", which has been widely touted as a concept.

It was not until 2012 that there was significant growth in crowdfunding and that it was considered globally important and not just as usual. The 2.5 million euros collected that year in cultural projects and charitable organizations in all spheres of Spain.

3 Trends And 3 Pillars Of Crowd Support

Crowdfunding is based on 3 online trends:

Collaborative use (e.g. sharing a house or car, eliminating contacts).

Peer-to-peer lending (peer-to-peer lending).

The 3 main pillars of current crowdfunding are:

Creator: It is the facilitator of the idea or project for which funding is requested. It should be a person who creates self-confidence, so anonymity is not recommended. It should be a person or group that has ownership on social media.

A project or idea: Being a new project (providing a different solution to the problem), a new one (without market presence) and generating value in the world (that it was actually claimed by someone other than the real creator). It should be transmitted or communicated in video format and, if possible, in prototype.

Refund or reward: It is beneficial. There must be a clear relationship between the amount requested and the amount provided as a refund. It is something that determines the market itself. For this reason, it is recommended that you look at at least 12 crowdfunding campaigns before designing your own, to see what rewards are offered, what type, and how much money is being requested. The reward can be a kiss, a percentage of the company or the project itself to be presented, but it should always be a refund of the requested amount. The campaign usually has several reward levels, depending on the different prices requested (for example, a reward of 5 euros, one of 15 euros, one of 25 euros, and so on).

TYPES OF CROWDFUNDING

According to the European Association of crowdfunding, there are four types of crowdfunding-

Reward-Based Crowdfunding- This crowdfunding method is probably the most popular and comes in forums like Kickstarter and Indiegogo. With reward-based fundraising, people can promise money for creative projects, new pieces of technology, or any other product or service. What makes it so successful is that sponsors who accumulate projects in the forums receive benefits or rewards when they donate their money to the right projects or companies.

While it may seem easy enough to post a project online, there are many attempts at it before it can successfully receive funding. Getting thousands of people to contribute to a

project requires the same if not extra attention, planning, and acting like any other successful marketing or fundraising campaign.

Equity Crowdfunding: Award-based crowd sponsors make donations to win awards and complete satisfaction of helping companies achieve their goals. On the other hand, equity crowd sponsors provide companies with operating capital to acquire a company piece. Usually, to get a business down or to give it a lot of money, entrepreneurs often turn to foreign investors for more money.

Equity crowdfunding allows investors to participate in the company's limited ownership because each of them receives a share of the company and a percentage of the profits. This can be beneficial in the beginning because it is a quick way to earn money. However, this can be difficult when it comes to legal requirements. This is because it allows for a large number of equal investors in the business. As a result, business owners may lose some of their power.

Donation-Based Crowdfunding: GoFundMe is an excellent example of a platform that uses donor crowdfunding. This type of crowdfunding is often used by non-profit organizations that require donations to raise funds for their causes. Most donors who donate money for these platforms usually do not expect to give back and donate to the topic or organization they support. In all cases, the ROI (return on investment) arises from the personal satisfaction that comes from contributing to the project.

Peer-to-Peer Lending: In the past, peer lending meant borrowing money from loved ones to finance a business. However, these days, platforms like Lending Club and Prosper have emerged to use the same concept in fundraising. This allows beginners to access finances outside of conventional lending channels.

CROWD FUNDING EDUCATION

Today, there could be a various reason to consider crowd funding; it could be entrepreneurial ventures, social cause, higher studies, music albums or videos, gigs and festivals, publishing books, mega events or college projects. There are different forms of crowd funding available. It could be reward based, loan based or equity based. However, in India, the most popular way of securing funds, is the rewards or returns based funding. On being questioned as to their willingness to support educational cause, the respondents were of the view point that they would surely contribute to the cause of furtherance of education. On being asked about the factors influencing their decision for contributing towards education, the respondents felt that they would prefer financing students who are from weak financial backgrounds and performing well academically.

CROWD SOURCING EDUCATION

Education to help more people and learning is not limited to campus boundaries. Information on all types of courses and courses is now available online. This wealth of information comes from the crowd and can be replanted in the classroom or beyond. Visual classes have gained importance these days. Online courses are becoming more and more popular. Many US universities also have their own forums to encourage students and academics to apply for financial assistance for their projects, and it is becoming increasingly common in the UK.

CROWDS FOR CROWDFUNDING

Very popular: People donate money to get something (reward). It is governed by the rules of e-commerce and data privacy. Funds are requested to receive prizes that are consistent with all budgets. It can be digital or virtual prizes. Customers, who show that the project makes sense in the market, are wanted. The mass rewards campaign helps to ensure the project, to grow it, to see how difficult it is to reach the target audience.

Donors know that a product or service is a model and that it will take time for them to develop a real product. Usually, these people give a lot of feedback instead of how they want that product. Divided into:

Reward crowdfunding "all or nothing".

If the requested amount is not met, no fee is available.

Therefore, it is recommended that you request the minimum required for the project to proceed.

Reward crowdfunding "everything is important".

All euros that go into the campaign are brought to the creator of the project. With this type of campaign there is a problem with confidence: Once we have said we need an "X" of value to put a job, we have to show how we will put the job if we get less money. Therefore, it applies to very modular projects.

MOST CROWDFUNDED PLATFORM IN EDUCATIONAL SITES

1. **DonorsChoose-** This nonprofit crowdfunding platform makes it easy to raise money for any classroom in need of funds online.
2. **GiveCampus-** Give Campus partners with colleges to help students, alumni, parents, and faculty launch fundraisers for school-related projects.
3. **Piggybackr-** is a US crowdfunding website for students and youth teams to fundraise for their schools, projects, and causes online. It is compliant with the American Children's Online Privacy Protection Act, meaning that children as young as 5 can run fundraising projects on-line. Backers of projects can post public comments, but cannot communicate directly with the children posting projects. Children under the age of 13 must have parental involvement with their projects.
4. **GoFundMe-** is an American for-profit crowdfunding platform that allows people to raise money for events ranging from life events such as celebrations and graduations to challenging circumstances like accidents and illnesses. From 2010 to the beginning of 2020, over \$9 billion has been raised on the platform, with contributions from over 120

million donors

5. **FundRazr-** is a free crowdfunding and online fundraising platform released in 2009. FundRazr operates internationally in 35+ countries with the largest markets being United States, Canada, United Kingdom and Australia. It allows users to run a wide-range of crowdfunding campaigns by creating fundraising pages and sharing it via social media, messaging apps, email and more to raise money for over 100 types of causes such as nonprofit, medical care, education, community help, poverty alleviation, arts, memorials, and animal rescue causes.

6. **Fundly-** Fundly is a crowdfunding site for online fundraising. It allows non-profits, charities, politics, clubs, schools, teams, churches, and other causes to raise money online from friends, family, colleagues, donors, and other supporters via email, Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn, Google, and social media networks.

7. **Classy-** Classy is a software company and online fundraising platform designed for nonprofit organizations. Headquartered in San Diego, California, Classy was founded by CEO Scot Chisholm, Pat Walsh, and Marshall Peden in 2006, originally to host fundraising events that benefit charities.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Ethan Mollick (2014) Crowdfunding allows the founders of to make a profit, arts, and culture to fund their finances efforts by taking small donations compared to a very large number of people using the Internet, and there are no regulated financial intermediaries. Author notes that a large number of founders appear to meet their obligations to sponsors, however that is over 75% bring sales later than expected, with predictable rate of delay in quantity and value financing an acquired project. These results provide insight on the growing development of crowdfunding, as well as the warehouse light on the ways in which the actions of the founders may have effect on their ability to access business support.

LoretaValančienė (2015) In this issue, a list of crowdfunding agencies and their pursuits provided in addition to a high view of crowdfunding guidelines in countries such as USA, UK, Canada,Germany, France, Australia and Italy. Author also they recommend that although all nations are progressing legal entities, enlightening entrepreneurs and to promote good fundraising cases, various actions which includes selling an excellent crowdfunding label websites, educating investors and conducting an overview of true crowdfunding platforms are made up of only a few service providers.

Prinsha K. (2016) A common trading method business finances are particularly opposed to crowdfunding. Traditionally, starting a business or introducing a new product the entrepreneur should do market research, put together a business plan, and create a prototype to validate concept and look for investors to help the business financially. These financing services include banks,angelic buyers and share money businesses, which really limited some alternatives to more than one key players. This method of raising money may seem appropriate,which rises in large-scale investments and investor targets market at the closed give up. This approach is amazing directs the traditional model, giving the entrepreneur a one platform for their construction, demonstration and sharing skills.

Irma Borst, Et.al, (2018) Crowd funding includes expansion a small amount of money from many investors,usually via the Internet and social media, to sponsor a new project. Looking at the mechanics of the machines thinking of attracting great support remote potential applications over current networks evaluate the use of social media as well crowdfunding forum.

EDTECH MARKET

Edtech market is becoming increasingly complex and flexible and constantly changing with stakeholders such as retailers, technology platform providers; content developers; teachers; students; institutions such as clients, investors, regulators, governments. Edtech market is diverse, with big players like Byjus and small beginners trying their hands in India. The availability of cheap internet connectivity with reasonable bandwidth through digital forums increases daily demand. These Edtech companies promise the delivery of quality education and easy access at a low cost compared to traditional classroom delivery environments. Covid-19 pandemic, while playing havoc on the life of people, also planted the seeds of the digital learning model in the education sector.

The influence of such Edtech companies in the ever-increasing digital space in the education sector is growing day by day, especially in the post-Covid-19 pandemic. The governments and its regulators were waiting for a long time to introduce large-scale technical innovations through education technology to scale up the outreach and improve the gross enrollment ratio (GER) in schools and colleges/universities. They want to transform the teaching-learning process in the education sector and

introduce analytical tools to evaluate the investment made in the education sector. The unexpected impetus to Edtech post-Covid-19 brought several challenges to the stakeholders viz. learners, educators, administrators, governments, and employers in various forms in the admission process, access to physical books, face-to-face interaction with teachers and their peer groups. However, the Edtech companies quickly stepped in at the early stage of remote learning. They provided online solutions by helping the institutions to hold online admissions tests, proctored examinations, and digital content in a collaborative role.

FUNDING OF EDTECH START-UPS ECO SYSTEM

India has been constantly climbing the ladder of innovation and the first ecosystem. Today the Indian Edtech start up ecosystem uses state-of-the-art technology to attract the attention of the industry, emerging capitalists, corporations, and governments. Many of them have successfully used prototypes to attract investment. They have successfully attracted large-scale investment, which encourages continued growth of the sector,

especially during and after the Covid-19 epidemic. The Edtech industry provides angels and corporate investors with the opportunity to earn a significant financial return while helping the cause of education in the country.

The demand for Edtech services has brought many investment opportunities in venture capital (VC) and listed figures. The Covid-19 problem does not go away and comes back one way or another. In that case, it will accelerate investment early in Edtech. According to the latest figures compiled by Tracxn Technology Limited, a Bangalore- based company that helps Investors get started, about 8768 EdTech Start-ups companies are now based in India (Tracxn, 2021). Four of them - Byju (\$ 16.5 billion), Unacademic (\$ 3.4 billion), Eruditus (\$ 3.2 billion), and UpGrad (\$ 1.2 billion) have now become unicorns (Business Insider India, 2021).

The entry point for Edtech companies in India is to use one or more combinations of (a) Shared Business; (b) cooperation; (c) Franchise; As the industry reveals, of the top ten companies that attracted investment from 5 million to 200 million by 2020, eight were in the test preparation phase, one in K-12, skills development, business solution, and certification. . Access to higher education is still lacking. Financial business education finance globally The 2021 analytical report published by HolonIQ in early 2022 shows that Chinese EdTech investment is falling with impressive investment growth in the US and Europe. From \$ 1 billion in 2014, Indian Edtech startups reached \$ 3.8 billion by 2021 and positioned it near the United States (\$ 8.3 billion). Europe (\$ 3.0 billion) is the third most popular region, followed by China (\$ 2.7 billion). China's investment started at \$ 0.6 billion in 2014 and grew to \$ 10.2 billion by 2020 and suddenly dropped to \$ 2.7 billion by 2021. In the case of the United States, there is a significant increase from \$ 2.5 billion by 2020 to \$ 8.3 billion. Europe's growth is almost identical to that of India, which started at \$ 1 billion in 2014 and reached \$ 3.0 billion by 2021. India has now become the leading investor in Asia at the beginning of Edtech, surpassing Europe, yet the sector is not much different.

EDTECH ADOPTION IN POST COVID-19 PANDEMIC

Many schools and institutions of higher learning had switched to digital to offer education for the first time, and, in the middle of the night, it happened. However, it cannot be said that moving from offline mode to offline was a hassle because there were no participants, i.e., teachers, students, or staff, trained to manage their new delivery delivery tools. Many have tried to replicate classes and laboratories to better understand their students at their level with the tools available. Many institutions have begun to invest heavily in technology-driven programs such as hardware, software content, and training to create online and integrated systems in order to improve efficiency and overcome problems of access to education in remote areas. In order to enhance and support modern teaching, there is an urgent need for the integration of classrooms, seminars, and conference rooms with Edtech-based services once students or students return to campuses. Today, all institutions predict that visual learning will not end even after this epidemic next year. Practical learning with the help of Edtech companies charges a new chapter in human learning history. Rethinking how to bring educational resources to the institutional environment. However, the challenge lies in how the education ecosystem is prepared to embrace the digital transformation opportunities brought about by the epidemic. The Institute's digitization process involves five steps: a) Digging information by transforming the physical form information process into a digital format. b) Organize information by changing the correct vertical position. c) Automatic process through digital technology with the help of institutional equipment or by partnering with Edtech. d) Simplifying the process, including evaluation. e) Finally, transform the educational institution. The final step can only be achieved after a series of steps / processes, the working culture of employees, and the transition to a new digital driven business and business model for value proposition. The World Bank is a major financial institution in more than 80 underdeveloped or developing countries around the world. According to their report, “many countries are now considering a dual role for learning in remote areas: as a policy for future disaster risk management, especially in a climate change climate and how to reach school children and provide lifelong education for all citizens.

In contrast, there are a number of challenges that Edtech companies are currently facing. There is a delay in obtaining a patent under the Indian Copyright Act and the Patent Office. On average, it takes 3 to 4 months to complete a certificate. There is a lack of digital readiness in institutions. Most of these institutions are funded by government agencies such as the School Office or Higher Education at the District Government level and at the Central level through the University Grants Commission. The lack of strong IT and connectivity / bandwidth, especially in rural, back-and-forth areas, is also hampering the growth of Edtech companies in India. The Edtech market in India is very competitive, and it is crowded and operates in a small area. Of the 4500 Edtech initiatives operating in this field, only a few have achieved promotions and positive pre-profit profits, taxes, depreciation, amortization (EBITDA) margins.

The governing bodies in the higher education sector do not support Edtech companies that are replacing online degree programs in partnership with HEIs. India is a multilingual country, Edtech donations need to be customized, and companies may incur additional costs and eliminations for regional players. Most companies focus exclusively on the K-12 market segment preparation test, which leaves the competition for higher education. There is a lack of variance in the supply market because the cost could not determine the cost. There is a growing need for players to focus on classification without raising the bar. Most Edtech startups are unable to keep the customer afloat, leading to failure on delivery. There is a lack of funding for access to more expensive digital programs to facilitate online learning and sustainability. High advertising reduces the chances of earning money from investors and grants. Companies spend a lot of money on online advertising and promotions of up to 200 to 400 percent of their operating income in the hope of achieving a desirable growth rate. Once they reach their target, they reduce marketing costs by 40 to 50 percent. India's education system continues to be a test subject due to public pressure to do well in competitive exams to get into university education. Adapting to a new digital culture in schools and HEIs may take longer. With the exception of a few, most of the investors in the EdTech field are specialists or regular business funds, and many of the most heavily funded companies are located in areas where these investors are beginning to seek out. A growing number

of IPOs (First Public Offerings) are listed by VCs or discarded by their corporate owners. Therefore, there is a need for public funding in the EdTech sector.

The public sector in India has been instrumental in bringing about digital revolution in every possible way, and the government is investing heavily in such programs. In recent years all governments and founders have invested heavily in education. It has, in a sense, enabled Edtech companies to gain power. Millions of users have started using in- app learning during the Covid-19 era. “Flexible and personalized learning is becoming more common among teenagers and school children. Many urban schools are starting to use this technology, and young teachers are increasingly coming to run the learning process. According to figures provided by the Invest India program by the Government of India, by 2020, India has emerged as the most vibrant and fast-growing digital economy with a large consumer base. India gains the mark for the installation of 2018 billion applications making up 14 percent worldwide. Recently, guidelines were issued by the University Grants Commission and the All-India Council for Technical Education at all universities and technical institutions to ensure that there are no job vacancies at Edtech companies while offering online degree programs.

Strengths

- (a) Cost effective
- (b) Flexible reading
- (c) Learning success
- (d) Personal study
- (e) Access to inaccessible markets
- (f) Scale and integrity
- (g) Industrial and educational co-operation
- (h) Skills development
- (i) Provides better co-ordination and governance

(j) It is easy to collect feedback and analysis

Weaknesses

(a) Edtech cannot replace traditional education

(b) Education reform

(c) Disturbance by students and they were constantly tempted to use distractions

(d) a lack of critical views from teachers and a lack of transparency

(e) Students are not motivated and do not have a proper reporting system

(f) Potential melting of the contribution level

(g) Privacy and security of data matters

(h) The concept of cultural-Indian education system continues to be guided by testing

(i) Customer concepts- Clients seeking value addition to existing services

Opportunities

(a) Digital Communication

(b) Flexible Reading

(c) Personal Information

(d) Number of urban dwellers hungry for content: Improved internet communication

(e) Professional career opportunities and leisure or independent activities

(f) Government support for digital transformation in the education sector

(g) Company Training Programs and Management Development Programs

Challenges

- a) IPR problems
- b) Digital readiness and unavailability of strong IT and network / bandwidth in non-urban areas
- c) Dealing with Strong Competition
- d) Minimum interest rate
- e) Governing bodies in the higher education sector do not support collaboration with universities
- f) Road misunderstandings- Global compared to local
- g) Edtech Dense Area: focuses only on K-12 segment Preparation Examination;
- h) Lack of segregation and customer retention

NEED FOR STUDY

For most of the parents and students, sometimes it looks like trouble to manage information about the availability of forms, brochures, and important dates, etc. Most of the student who opted for science stream are willing to take Btech CS. For the several institutes and universities. Students don't want to break continuity and have a plan for instant admission to colleges after the intermediate examination. For this reason, they appear in more than one entrance exam, and they get shortlisted in the various general and professional courses as per their preparation and performance. In this case, it becomes difficult to opt for the right course to give a new dimension to your career to achieve your long-term goals. In such a case, a counsellor may play a vital role in boosting students' morale. Counselling helps students to identify the right career opportunity. The counsellor should explore their aptitude, areas of interest, and abilities first and then give a pathway to success. Most of the Indian universities are open to free online counselling to take admission in various professional courses, viz. B.Tech, B.Arch., B.Des, B.Pharm, MBA, MFM, MCA, MBBS, BDS, and B.Ed., etc. Students find themselves confident about the choice of career option. The selection of the right course for graduation is most important because it's the first brick career foundation.

RESULT OF STUDY

Our analysis produced a total of 207 educational campaigns related to mass fundraising from May 1 to May 19, 2019. Most of the first educational technology campaigns used RocketHub , followed by Kick starter , and Indigo . Only three campaigns have been submitted to Mycroryza, and only one project has chosen to use Peer Backers as its platform to support more people. This was an amazing event because we were expecting the Kickstarter platform to be a complete leader due to its initial and largest funding base. Additionally, it was surprising to find that platforms like I am Scientist, which focuses on helping young researchers, as well as Start Some Good, which provides support to nonprofits and social entrepreneurs, were not represented in our sample. Top 10 successfully funded projects based on the percentage of funding (i.e., the amount requested compared to the amount generated).

These projects include a Python programming language e-book, an interactive multimedia online tutorial on Word press content management system, a smart card game and mobile applications to teach pronunciation and spelling, gamma particle detector, video tutorial. in game programming, hardware platform for learning basic engineering concepts and programs, Linux interactive 3D game and systems for security systems for hackers, full-featured PHP for beginners, DVD for effective ash application, and summer week program 10 web design tutorials for teens from Chicago's Englewood area. Six of the top ten most popular fundraising campaigns focus on reading materials (e-books, entertainment games) or training programs (online tutorial, video tutorial, summer camp) focused on teaching and learning programming languages. or pro gramming sites (Linux in a Hack venture game).

Most of these projects were specifically targeted for informal reading or could be used in both formal and informal reading settings (e.g., e-books). He points out that we have seen that many education-focused projects deployed in the crowdfunding forums we have reviewed are designed to support learning in an informal, off-school environment. In fact, the most popular project to 1,588 supporters was an e-book entitled

Many of the most successful projects funded in our research were very small in terms of the funding they requested from the community. This supports the results of a previous study that analyzed the data set of more than 48,500 projects with a combined funding of more than \$ 237M and revealed that smaller policies were more effective in funding than larger ones . The result means that education technology professionals should consider designing a series of campaigns for their major projects, combining these projects into smaller stages of development and productivity.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

1. Sampling Techniques In this study, a convenient sampling technique is used to collect the data.
2. Sampling Size 50 respondents were surveyed among young entrepreneurs in Delhi NCR and Bihar.
3. Data collection method The study is primarily focused on primary data by issuing a questionnaire to the respondents, and the secondary data was acquired by means of news articles and websites.
4. . 4. Study area The research study was made in Delhi NCR and Bihar.
5. Study period The period of the study was from March 2022 to May 2022.

OBJECTIVE OF THE PROJECT

- 1- To know the awareness and willingness to use Crowdfunding among the young people.
- 2- To study about the various education crowdfunding platforms in india.

RESEARCH HYPOTHESIS

Counselling can be a difficult process and there many factors that can contribute towards the success of the engagement or otherwise lead to zero or negative gains.

DATA ANALYSIS

Descriptive analytic approach was used to analyze the data. Value of knowledge, attitude and behavior questionnaires divided into three categories: low, fairly and high.. While the development of learning media about people with special needs data was described as indicators for developing the learning media.

Based on the results of students' awareness data towards, the results are as follows: 1. Interacting with people with special needs The results of the data on the level of interacting with people with special needs can be seen in Figure 1.

2. Location
37 responses

Based on Figure 1, it is known that out of 37 respondents, 30 % of respondents are from Delhi . About 38 % respondents are from Noida and 27% from Bihar region . Only few % of respondents are from other state/province.

3. Have you ever been involved in crowdfunding for ?

37 responses

4. Are you Aware about Crowdfunding ?

37 responses

5. Which of the following non-crowdfunding means of support for sustainability have you participated in over the past 12 months ?

37 responses

6. Have you tried to get financing from other sources launching your campaign ?

37 responses

7. How can you create a good crowdfunding pitch to finance your education?

37 responses

8. What are some of the common challenges of crowdfunding for university?

37 responses

- a) Creating a good crowdfunding pitch.
- b) Being consistent when it comes to marketing your campaign to encourage the public to donate to your cause.
- c) It might take longer than you'd expect to raise your goal.
- d) All of the above.

9. For what purpose you uses Crowdfunding ?

37 responses

- a) To find the newly startup projects/ company.
- b) To start a donation
- c) To finance an investment

10. Do you agree Crowdfunding of Educational Technology Startups is good in India ?

37 responses

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Disagree
- Strongly disagree
- Neutral

CONCLUSION

The growth motivation for Edtech eco-system in India lies in four factors - (a) the number of young people; (b) Increase parental income; (c) the low cost of internet data; and (d) cheap mobile learning gadgets. It is estimated that smartphone users will double in 2025 from 500 million by 2020. Admittedly, the implementation of Edtech has disrupted part of training and exam preparation, but they have not yet touched the core of the value chain of education. The introduction of digital technology into the education system can serve as a parallel and will not replace the traditional education system. Edtech companies should keep the truth in mind when designing their offerings.

Although the Covid-19 epidemic has accelerated the transformation of digital technology into the education sector, consistent efforts must be made by Edtech companies to keep interest alive among stakeholders. It is possible with ongoing innovations and new offerings. When the epidemic is over, schools / colleges reopened, normalcy restored; student retention may cause problems in these Edtech forums. Edtech beginners face complex challenges such as low customer base, inability to determine the right number of offerings, lack of diversity, lack of product division, high customer acquisition. Edtech emerging players must use a variety of strategies to survive in a crowded environment.

They have to rely heavily on extension, innovation, integration, approval of student results, and fragmentation. Edtech beginners should use Augmented Reality (AR) and Virtual Reality (VR) extensively to provide better user experience and bring realistic learning features that can be brought to the place of a traditional, offline classroom. Edtech beginners need to focus on acquiring new digital skills to prepare students for future roles in the job market. Diversity in the nearby Edtech segment is also a good option for an extended survival company. There are successful beginners who participate in student learning and teaching notes. MOOCs are also another way to use higher education and business students. Now is the time for higher education institutions to establish good relations with Edtech companies. The level of

contribution of their program is not refined but improved to achieve growth and goals. The future of the study space will be small in the visual infrastructure and large in the digital space, and Edtech could play a role in empowering GER development. Edtech is expected to play a role in motivating and helping institutions to improve their studies and meet the needs of hungry young students.

LIMITATION

- It will not necessarily be an easier process to go through compared to the more traditional ways of raising finance - not all projects that apply to crowdfunding platforms get onto them
- When you are on your chosen platform, you need to do a lot of work in building up interest before the project launches - significant resources (money and/or time) may be required
- If you don't reach your funding target, any finance that has been pledged will usually be returned to your investors and you will receive nothing
- Failed projects risk damage to the reputation of your business and people who have pledged money to you
- If you haven't protected your business idea with a patent or copyright, someone may see it on a crowdfunding site and steal your concept
- Getting the rewards or returns wrong can mean giving away too much of the business to investors

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APPENDICES

1. Your Name

2. Location
a) Delhi
b) Noida
c) Bihar
d) Others

3. Have you ever been involved in crowdfunding for ?
a) Yes
b) No

4. Are you Aware about Crowdfunding ?
a) Yes
b) No

5. Which of the following non-crowdfunding means of support for sustainability have you participated in over the past 12 months ?
a) Donations
b) Rewards
c) Equity/bond
d) Lending

6. Have you tried to get financing from other sources launching your campaign ?
a) Yes - a bank loan
b) Yes - venture capital
c) Yes - business angels
d) Yes - friends and family

7. How can you create a good crowdfunding pitch to finance your education?
a) Highlight what makes you different from other students who are crowdfunding for university , as well as what you've done to help yourself
b) Highlight that you can't afford your degree and need the help of good-willing donors

8. What are some of the common challenges of crowdfunding for university?
 - a) Creating a good crowdfunding pitch.
 - b) Being consistent when it comes to marketing your campaign to encourage the public to donate to your cause.
 - c) It might take longer than you'd expect to raise your goal.
 - d) All of the above.

9. For what purpose you uses Crowdfunding ?
 - a) To find the newly startup projects/company.
 - b) To start a donation
 - c) To finance an investment

10. Do you agree Crowdfunding of Educational Technology Startups is good in India ?
 - a) Strongly agree
 - b) Agree
 - c) Neutral
 - d) Disagree
 - e) Strongly disagree

PLAGIARISM SCAN REPORT

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Awareness Towards education among students in delhi Ncr

Edtech companies that accumulate sponsorship on social media are ten pennies right now. We wanted to be able to dig a little deeper and understand how investor react to edtech programs on these sites. Crowdfunding is a fundraiser where creators of an idea or business or community project ask for financial support from strangers who want to participate by developing small amounts of money to get the latest prize. Remember that crowdfunding only helps sponsorships, but not the process of creating or distributing sponsored product or services.

While crowdfunding brings as the new thing the fact that it is done online, it is not a new approach. It already existed before the advent of the internet and came from sponsoring and promoting projects by the community. Undoubtedly it was crowdfunding "offline". It was a gift from the French people to the American people and represented freedom.

Crowdfunding also stands for that freedom, in the sense that it allows for retirement to depend on the many institutions that have so far hindered the efficiency of entrepreneurs when presenting their own projects. It is part of a business-based practice among people, from which consultants are removed. In December 2006, there were no business angels investing in startups in Spain. Government institutions did not support new projects in new technologies or the Internet, as ENISA, CDTI, and others now do; and there were no special investment funds at first, although there were technology entrepreneurship projects.

From the Internet bubble: From 2000 to 2005 almost no one dared to invest in the network. However, in 2005 there was a resurgence powered by new trends from Silicon Valley and the beginning of social media and e-commerce. At that time there were entrepreneurs who wanted to do things, but there were no investors or banks or institutions to support them. Entrepreneurs therefore consider investing in "2.0 web companies", which has been widely touted as a concept. It was not until 2012 that there was significant growth in crowdfunding and that it was considered globally important and not just as usual. The 2.5 million euros collected that year in cultural projects and charitable organizations in all spheres of Spain.

3 Trends And 3 Pillars Of Crowd
Support Crowdfunding is based on 3

online trends:

Collaborative use (e.g. sharing a house or car, eliminating contacts).Peer-to-peer lending (peer-to-peer lending).

Sources	Similarity
<p>elearningindustry.com > crowdfunding-in-education Crowdfunding In Education - eLearning Industry</p> <p>We came from the internet bubble: From 2000 to 2005 almost no one dared to invest in the network. However, in 2005 there was a resurgence powered by the new trends coming from Silicon Valley and the beginning of social networking and e-commerce.</p> <p>https://elearningindustry.com/crowdfunding-in-education/</p>	<p>6%</p>

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Happy Learning.

- “Academic Writing” Team (The Team AW)

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